

A Polarographic Study of Copper-8-aminoquinoline Complex

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A polarographic study of copper-8-aminoquinoline complex has been made in 50% dioxane medium. Copper ion has been found to combine with 8-aminoquinoline in the ratio of 1:2, involving two electrons in the process of reduction. The dissociation constant of the complex has been found to be 1.55×10^{-9} . The increase in dioxane concentration decreases the stability of the complex.

Complexes of a number of cations with 8-aminoquinoline have been reported¹. In the case of copper, two complexes, $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{N}_2)^{2+}$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{N}_2)_2^{2+}$, have been reported. The former was obtained when the amount of the reagent was deficient, whereas the latter was obtained on addition of an excess of the reagent. 8-Aminoquinoline has also been used for gravimetric determination of copper and its separation from a number of other cations². Recently this reagent has been used for spectrophotometric determination of palladium³. It is of interest to note that on addition of sodium hydroxide, the insoluble cationic complex of palladium becomes non-ionic, in which one of the hydrogen atoms of the NH_2 group is replaced.

EXPERIMENTAL

A Cambridge pen-recording polarograph and a saturated calomel electrode in conjunction with the polarographic cell through a KCl-agar bridge were used for taking all current-voltage data. A Metrohm pH-meter, model E-350, was used for measurements of pH. Temperature was kept constant at $30^\circ \pm 1^\circ$.

Copper sulphate (A.R., B.D.H.) was used for preparing standard solutions. For suppression of maxima, a 0.01% solution of gelatin was added to all solutions. Dioxane was purified by refluxing with metallic sodium and then distilling it over sodium before use. As 8-aminoquinoline is insoluble in water, all studies were carried out in 50% dioxane. All other reagents used were of high purity.

A cupric-ion concentration of $1 \times 10^{-3}M$ was maintained for all the readings. Potassium nitrate (0.1M) was used as the supporting electrolyte.

Good polarographic waves were not obtained with copper-8-aminoquinoline complex at low concentrations of the reagent immediately after mixing and all solutions to be examined were kept overnight. This seems to be due to the fact that complex formation

1. Burrow and Ritchie, *J. Proc. Roy. Soc., N. S. Wales*, 1939, 72, 113.
2. Bankovskis, *Latvijas PSR Cinatnu Acad. Vestis*, 1955, No. 9, 115.
3. Gustin and Sweet, *Anal. Chem.*, 1963, 35, 44.

takes place slowly. Half-wave potentials were measured both as a function of 8-aminoquinoline concentration and pH . While plotting the curves $[\log (i_d - i)/i \text{ vs. } E_{d.e}]$, corrections were made for residual current. Values of half-wave potentials were taken from logarithmic plots. $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ values were generally reproducible to ± 2 mv.

DISCUSSION

On plotting $\log (i_d - i)/i$ against $E_{d.e}$, the slopes of the curves are found equal to $+0.036$ approximately in all cases, showing that the system is sufficiently reversible. This also shows that two electrons are involved in the process of reduction.

Half-wave potentials of the copper complex over the concentration range of 0.008

FIG. 1
A. In absence of buffer.
B. In presence of phosphate buffer.

pH values ranging from 5.9 to 8.4. Dissociation constant of the copper complex was calculated using the equation;

$$(E_{\frac{1}{2}})_c - (E_{\frac{1}{2}})_s = 0.0296 \log K_d - 0.0296 \times p \times \log C_x.$$

In the above expression $(E_{\frac{1}{2}})_c$ and $(E_{\frac{1}{2}})_s$ are half-wave potentials for the complex and the simple metal ions respectively; p is the number of ligand molecules in combination with a copper ion, which is two in this case; C_x is the concentration of the free ligand in the solution. The data obtained are recorded in Table I.

Effect of Dioxane Concentration.—It has been shown by a number of workers that the presence of dioxane weakens the metal—ammine bond⁴. This has also been found

4. "Stability Constants. Part I. Organic Ligands", 1957, The Chemical Society, London.

to 0.1M of 8-aminoquinoline in 0.1M KNO_3 as the supporting electrolyte are plotted against logarithm of 8-aminoquinoline concentration in Fig. 1 (curve A). Similar studies were made in presence of 0.01M phosphate buffer in the concentration range of 0.01 to 0.1M of 8-aminoquinoline (Fig. 1, curve B). The slopes of the two curves are 0.060 and 0.059 respectively, showing that divalent copper ion combines with 8-aminoquinoline in the ratio of 1:2.

A study of the above complex at various pH values between 5.9 and 8.4, keeping the ligand concentration constant, shows no variation in half-wave potential with pH , showing that the same complex is formed at different

to be the case by the authors. The complex was studied in 20 to 60% dioxane medium and the increase in dioxane concentration was found to decrease the stability of the complex formed. The results of these investigations are shown in Table II.

TABLE I

Effect of ligand concentration on $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ of copper-8-aminoquinoline complex.

$Cu^{2+} = 1 \times 10^{-3}M$. $KNO_3 = 0.1M$. Gelatin = 0.01%.

Total ligand molarity.	Free ligand molarity.	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ vs.S.C.E.	K_d (calc.).
A. Without buffer.			
6×10^{-3}	4.0×10^{-3}	-0.1025	1.500×10^{-9}
8×10^{-3}	6.0×10^{-3}	-0.1125	1.528
1×10^{-2}	8.0×10^{-3}	-0.1200	1.507
2×10^{-2}	1.8×10^{-2}	-0.1400	1.607
4×10^{-2}	3.8×10^{-2}	-0.1600	1.528
6×10^{-2}	5.8×10^{-2}	-0.1700	1.622
8×10^{-2}	7.8×10^{-2}	-0.1775	1.637
10×10^{-2}	9.8×10^{-2}	-0.1850	1.449
			Av. 1.55×10^{-9}
B. With phosphate buffer (pH 6.85).			
1.0×10^{-2}	8.0×10^{-3}	-0.1200	1.503
2.0×10^{-2}	1.8×10^{-2}	-0.1390	1.739
4.0×10^{-2}	3.8×10^{-2}	-0.1590	1.629
8.1×10^{-2}	7.9×10^{-2}	-0.1770	1.500
10×10^{-2}	9.8×10^{-2}	-0.1830	1.698

TABLE II

Effect of dioxane concentration on the stability of copper-8-aminoquinoline complex.

The conditions are the same as in Table I.

Dioxane conc(%)	20	30	40	50	60
$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ vs.S.C.E	-0.162	-0.162	-0.146	-0.140	-0.135
K_d	2.94×10^{-10}	6.30×10^{-10}	1.01×10^{-9}	1.007×10^{-9}	2.399×10^{-9}

Nature of the Red Colour Produced by Cu^{2+} with 8-Aminoquinoline.—It was found that the light blue copper-8-aminoquinoline solutions, when kept for some time, developed a deep red colour in 50% dioxane solution. The same colour slowly developed in 50% dioxane solution of 8-aminoquinoline alone when kept exposed to air. No colour was, however, observed in 8-aminoquinoline solution in 50% dioxane when the solution was kept in a tightly stoppered bottle in nitrogen atmosphere, but it developed if a copper salt was also added. The development of colour was found to be dependent on the concentration of 8-aminoquinoline present and the intensity of colour increased rapidly with increase in pH. The copper-8-aminoquinoline complex was also studied in 50% ethanol where no red colour developed on keeping and $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ values were approximately the same as in 50%

dioxane, though the polarographic waves were not so good. These observations show that the red colour is in no way associated with the copper-8-aminoquinoline complex and is an extraneous phenomenon, which seems to be caused by the oxidation of 8-aminoquinoline; this reaction is catalysed by copper ions. Similar examples of oxidation of amines in presence of cupric ions have been reported by Fallab⁵.

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